

Formation of Stars – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the new framework, analysis of the spaces of stars formation via the coupling constants series in its first and third representation, i.e. net curvature and the arrow of time will be presented. The framework indicate rapid formation at first, which get slowed down by bigger and bigger formation clusters. That is by the principle of least variation. A prediction is made regarding the formation of stars, the liars closer to core should be more dense than the external liars. The prediction is made based on the coupling constants series.

Introduction

Quantum analysis of the formation of stars. First, we have arbitrary amounts of curvature vanishing into matter. We have proven this in the thesis. The rigorous description can be made using the Dirac delta variation:

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (1.1)$$

The arbitrary amount can appear or not appear. Overall two states. Than from that matter, there is the probability that net curvature, which is either prime or one, will appear, synonymous with the coupling constants series and bosonic fields.

$$\delta g = 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (1.11)$$

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t2 = Q(t + \Delta t + \Delta t) \quad (1.12)$$

Among those net curvatures there is the photon of course, associated with $N_V = +(5)$, now that we have the coupling constants series, presented in equations (1.31) to (1.35) we can analyze the formation of stars.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.31)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.32)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.33)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.34)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.35)$$

In previous papers we derived the principle of least curvature, as the series develop with time, the net is a smaller portion of the whole curvature clusters, and therefore weaker and weaker. In the context of stars formation it predicts the formation to be fast at the beginning. As the result of the rapid matter formations the clusters gets bigger and bigger, synonymous with saying that the arrow is now referring to higher terms, the net variations despite being bigger are smaller portion of the whole, i.e. the star formation is now becomes slower and slower.

$$R = N_V / T_V \quad (1.36)$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 ... \quad (1.37)$$

It the net curvature is effecting the amount of matter being clustered than the core of the star would be denser than the outer liars formed later in time. Such an angle of analysis was not presented but it is reasonable to assume that the more curvature there is the more matter will be clustered. After the strong rapid formation causing the core to be dense, there are slower and slower formations building the external liars, and at later times the net curvature are so weak they have no effect on the formation of matter, maybe the scale of gravity. The description of the 8T framework can be analyzed by a simple prediction:

8T predicts a correlation between the core of a star to its mass density. The closer the mass liar to core the denser it should be.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)